

OCR quality assessment: Beyond ground truth

Giovanni Colavizza, Mirjam Cuper, Gijs Hendrikse, Bas Hofmans, Jamila Alsayed Kassem & Aurora Papotti

Introduction

Over the past years, considerable effort has been put into digitising library collections. As part of such efforts, the automatic extraction of text from images is of critical importance for making collections searchable and usable for both quantitative and qualitative analyses. This is the goal of Optical Character Recognition (OCR). OCR is difficult and error prone, especially so when considering historical documents and texts. Challenges arise from the support (e.g., bad preservation or fading ink) to the contents (e.g., language change) of such documents. Therefore, the topic of OCR quality evaluation has been getting increased attention in the literature and is of critical importance to inform libraries in their activities.

Typically, OCR quality is evaluated using “ground truth”: a high-quality, manually verified transcription that can be compared with the OCR-extracted text of the same document. Such evaluation is necessarily done on small samples, given the effort and cost of creating ground truth. This has several limitations: the scale of library collections and their variety make it always difficult to create a representative sample, therefore limiting the reliability of ground-truth-based OCR evaluations. This is why another line of work has focused on OCR quality assessment without ground truth. If successful, these methods promise to reduce the costs of OCR quality assessment substantially, thus making it a more widespread and common practice among libraries. The goal of the ICT with Industry KB challenge is to experiment with several, recently proposed techniques to assess the quality of OCR without ground truth, using a high-quality dataset provided by the KB. The main technique in this group, which will serve as a strong baseline, is lexicon-based evaluation or dictionary lookup. Finally, the challenge also serves to consolidate ongoing work between the KB and the research community on these topics. The open release of the evaluation data and challenge results is planned to this end.

Approaches

To evaluate how well the OCR evaluation metrics (without ground truth) reflect the quality of the text, we compare them with the established metrics that do build on ground truth. Specifically, we measure the correlation between the metrics under investigation and the Word/Character Error Rate (WER/CER). The higher the correlation between a metric and the WER or CER, the more likely it is to be a suitable measure for the OCR quality. We experimented with a variety of metrics that are described in recent literature.

1. Lexicon lookup

As a baseline to compare all methods to we implemented a lexical lookup method. For each OCR text the proportion of words present in the lexicon is measured, if it is present in the lexicon, it is more likely to be a correctly recognised word. As most lexicons of historical Dutch were created using the same data we were testing our methods on, we ended up creating our own lexicon using a data set of over 3000 manually corrected historical Dutch books from DBNL¹. Use of the lexicon lookup resulted in correlation with the word error rate between -0.7 and -0.8 , giving us a baseline performance. We also investigated the effect of using lexicons constructed for language from specific centuries to test for texts from these centuries as well. To this end lexicons were constructed

¹ <https://www.dbnl.org/>

from the DBNL books from specific centuries and performance was measured for texts from these centuries. Unfortunately, performance suffered significantly compared to using a general lexicon.

2. Fuzzy lexicon lookup

Exact matching might result in unfair/inaccurate evaluation of the OCR text, therefore a fuzzy lexicon lookup method was explored. Various tools for fuzzy search were investigated: Normalised Levenshtein distances, Damerau-Levenshtein and Optimal String Alignment. Unfortunately, there were not enough computational resources to implement and test these approaches on the provided datasets, leading to only be able to test the approach on a very small sample (5 items).

3. Character N-grams

Aside from the lexicon-based methods, we also investigated some lower-level lexical properties of the OCR text by looking at character N-grams. The hypothesis with this approach is that natural language typically uses only a subset of possible character N-grams. We have tried two character N-gram approaches: 1) create a lexicon of all used N-grams in the DBNL corpus and compute the ratio of N-grams of the OCR text that also occur in this lexicon, and 2) compute the relative frequencies of the top 10,000 character N-grams in the DBNL corpus to create a profile, and compute the cosine similarity between this profile and the profile created from the OCR text. Both approaches gave a high (negative) correlation between -0.7 and -0.8.

4. (Pseudo-)Perplexity

Instead of looking at lexical properties of the OCR text, we can also investigate its linguistic soundness. We can do this by taking a language model, pre-trained on a corpus like the DBNL dataset, and computing, for each token, the probability that it was generated by the language model, given the surrounding tokens. The more likely a token is according to the language model, the lower its perplexity is. We used the large language model BERTje² to compute pseudo-perplexities, giving us correlations between 0.3 and 0.7 - though the method was very slow on our laptop's small GPUs. We also considered historic language model GysBERT³, but unfortunately, this was trained on the data in the evaluation set provided by the KB.

5. Image features

With the hypothesis that the quality of the image can predict the quality of the resulting OCR, we tested two image-based approaches. For the first approach, we calculated image features score with an existing tool of the PRIMA research lab⁴. We compared the outcomes of every individual measure with the CER and WER but found no correlation. For the second approach, we used OpenCV to extract image features (e.g. brightness, contrast, noise). This led to a slightly higher correlation with the CER and WER.

Conclusion

Unfortunately, we did not have time to explore alternative metrics besides the ones already found in recent literature. However, we were able to show to the KB that the metrics that do not use ground truth definitely contain some signal and could prove suitable alternatives in the absence of ground

² W. de Vries, A. van Cranenburgh, A. Bisazza, T. Caselli, G. Noord and M. Nissim, "BERTje: A Dutch BERT Model" 2019, doi:10.48550/ARXIV.1912.09582

³ E. Manjavacas, L. Fonteyn, "Non-Parametric Word Sense Disambiguation for Historical Languages" *Proceedings of the 2nd International Workshop on Natural Language Processing for Digital Humanities (NLP4DH)*, Association for Computational Linguistics, 2022, pp.123-134.

⁴ C. Clausner, S. Pletschacher and A. Antonacopoulos, "Quality Prediction System for Large-Scale Digitisation Workflows," *2016 12th IAPR Workshop on Document Analysis Systems (DAS)*, Santorini, Greece, 2016, pp. 138-143, doi: 10.1109/DAS.2016.82.

truths. We hope the KB can use these results to improve their own OCR evaluation methods and implement (improvements on) some of the metrics we experimented with during the workshop.